

ADMINISTRATIVE COMPETENCY OF THE LEADER IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL OF TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this thesis, it is widely covered about continuous professional development of teachers, activation and support of the needs of self-personal development, formation of personal qualities of professional importance in professors and teachers during continuous professional development, and management competence of school principals.

Liberalization of the process of professional development of pedagogues requires limiting its mandatory forms and free choice of forms and periods of education in the pedagogical team and independently. The direction of the teacher's entire activity in the process of school and professional development, understanding of his personality and activity, should be focused on his reflection. Because pedagogical work does not develop without analysis and control. Regular analysis of one's own activity and comparison with others is a means of developing creativity and initiative. Liberalization of the process of teacher training should be based on the humanization of all its aspects.

Professional development of pedagogues is a separate link of the continuous education system, a relatively independent pedagogical system. As an independent pedagogical system, it is characterized by its structure, purpose, content, teaching forms and methods, subjects (teacher, methodologist, students) and socio-economic conditions, as well as the result (increased knowledge, skills, qualifications and pedagogical skills of students). . As long as teacher training is a pedagogical system with its own characteristics, it is first of all a system of training adults (that is, a person who has completed a certain stage of education and has an official document about his education), people with a certain social status in society, and professional people. the fact that such features are not fully taken into account by the teachers and organizers of the courses significantly reduces the effectiveness of the educational process in the courses. Conducting training without relying on teaching methods and forms, principles and laws specific to the existing system has become an image. Denial of the psychological characteristics of the trainees, their coursework, and the system as a whole, is the cause of the decrease in aspirations. It is possible to

radically restructure the teacher training system that takes into account various aspects of teachers' needs and characteristics - it is only possible to manage the teacher's pedagogical activity on the basis of reflexivity (intelligence). This means that a constant two-way connection between the teacher's pedagogical activity and its result can be realized through the development of special diagnostic procedures and technologies. The task of pedagogical diagnosis in the teacher training system is as follows: - to determine the possibilities of the single system of teacher training; - to find the positive and negative aspects of the activity of each link; - development of technologies aimed at improving the professional activity of teachers; - determining the sphere of influence of each link and defining the forms of two-way communication between them; - to find effective mechanisms of the teacher's work; - increasing the personal responsibility of the teacher in improving the education of students; - record the necessary knowledge, skills, qualifications for the teacher's professional level; - description of the relationship between the psychophysiological characteristics of teachers and their work and skills; - determining the optimal content, goal, form, method, means of education for the system of professional development. The conclusion is that the teacher's professional activity, regardless of what subject he teaches, is subject to a number of general requirements in the performance of pedagogical functions requires obedience, including the organization and implementation of group work of students, the selection of educational tools. This shows that fulfilling the requirements of a general didactic nature requires knowledge and skills from the teacher on the one hand, and on the other hand, it shows the existence of specific pedagogical difficulties. The students' learning of the methodology of diagnosing their own activities gives the opportunity to transfer the acquired knowledge and skills to their personal work style.

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